

Tool: Participatory symptoms mapping tool

Description	The tool consists of a map of the city, symptoms cards and pins. The map must clearly distinguish the different districts/neighborhoods within the urban area. Symptoms cards include: headache, itchy skin, respiratory difficulty, tiredness, nausea, itchy eyes, cough, congestion, and other (to ensure exhaustiveness).
Why am I doing it?	Investigate perceived symptoms of citizens due to traffic and contamination, by district of the city.
Which kind of issue can I tackle?	The tool was originally created for air pollution issues but can be adapted to other environmental concerns by outlining appropriate symptoms cards.
Resources needed	City map (A0); pins and symptoms cards; post-its; one facilitator to explain the task.
Time needed	20-30 minutes.
Skills needed (Not Required, Basic, Intermediate, Advanced)	<p>Subject-matter expertise: Basic</p> <p>IT skills: Basic</p> <p>Facilitation skills: Intermediate</p> <p>Event organization skills: Intermediate</p> <p>Project management skills: Basic</p> <p>Communication skills: Intermediate</p>
How to use the tool	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Either in conjunction with a public workshop or in other public places, create a separate space for engagement with a large map of the city and the symptoms cards. 2. Ask citizens and representatives of various institutions to map perceived symptoms when exposed to the environmental issue under investigation across the city's districts. 3. Gather further unstructured inputs from citizens through post-its – i.e. any additional insight beyond the simple symptom card. 4. Analyse symptoms by district and derive insights.
Outcomes	Refinement of citizens' concerns.
Tips!	<p>If the number of participants is high, it becomes practically difficult to keep the pins and the post-its ordered.</p> <p>Try to keep up with the conversation to gather additional annotations that can further explain the symptoms. While you won't require technical skills, you will have to empath!</p>

